

FEATURES OF SINGER-ILLUSTRATOR OCCUPATION. CHAMBER VOCAL MUSIC AS A FOUNDATION OF POINT “CONCERTMASTER”

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There are a couple of reasons to discuss this crucial part of musical upbringing among the young generation. Firstly, it has to be pointed out concertmaster is not only about the pianist, when the students are obtaining piano classes, they have several kinds of directions, and one of them is the concertmaster class, where the students are taught to accompany vocalists. Therefore, it is an essential profession to be an illustrator. He has to have an enormous repertoire of various romances, arias, and folk songs in different foreign languages. Moreover, his repertoire should include different range compositions for each level. As well, one of the important features of an illustrator's profession is voice health. Overwhelming is a constant companion for a singer, and they have to care about it. It is not necessary to sing without breaks for more than 40 minutes; singing in sickness, it affects the future condition of the voice. Moreover, it is not possible to sing unsuitable repertoire, for example, if you have a mezzo-soprano, you have to sing your own compositions. If only all of the singers could sing suitable arias and romances, they would save their voices in demand form. However, illustrators have to have certain skills because young musicians will be able to study in a proper way. For instance, a singer should be patient, listen carefully, and maintain playing while at the same time teaching a pupil to feel the ensemble between the piano and voice parts.

Definitely, the accompanist class is a complex system that includes work of the teacher, singer and student. In other words, it is a subject with more than one tutor. This tandem is necessary because there are a lot of vocal nuances. For instance, an opera genre, arias from operas, romances and chamber music are mainly used in musical education. Every single one has its own musical style, sound and performance manner. Accordingly, a singer has to be aware and have well done music skills. For example, Mozart's music belongs to 18th century, he is one of the greatest composers in history; he has written a huge number of vocal pieces, and his vocal compositions have been performed with a light bright sound, when it comes both a pianist and an accompanist. Another example is modern music of a composer of the 20th century. Let's take apart one of the

fascinating arias of Varvara from Rodion Shchedrin's opera "Not Only Love". This is a complicated masterpiece in modern music. Moreover, it has the hardest harmony; it consists of several different parts, including picturesque melodies. The piano part demands excellent technique and musicianship. When it comes to the voice part, it is necessary to have a deep understanding and virtuous vocal skills. The ensemble here is the hardest task for this performance; the singer should know their own part exactly. Furthermore, they have to control the piano part and the time frame. It makes sense to say about strokes.

Ensembles will be awesome if they use the proper touch of sound. There are a lot of strokes in music; legato, staccato, pizzicato, tough attack, and soft. It depends on the era, character, and style of play. Besides that, there is another complication: frequent tempo and rhythm changes. Juvenile students are not experienced enough, and their accompanists should maintain them, listen, and show them how it could be improved. When it comes to chamber music, it is definitely the pearl of art. Furthermore, they are complete vocal cycles, immersing themselves in deep emotions and imaginations, they could be named like a breathtaking picture. The main thing about that is to create music together. Astonishing vocal cycles, like Schubert's "The Winter Way", "The Beautiful Miller's Wife", "Leader", are excellent examples of learning. For instance, in the 19th song from "The Beautiful Miller's Wife", named "The Miller and the Stream", we can hear the conversation between them; the miller is suffering from a broken heart, we hear it like a slow, sad theme with steadily increasing intonations then the stream is answering; the piano part is showing it like murmuring water; using variations, the stream doesn't have a clue what love is and how painful to lose a beloved. After this, the miller would like to find calm at the bottom of the stream. Overall, it is a complex work with sound, balance, strokes, mood, breath, and technique.

